

LEIDEN UNIVERSITY &
GOVERNMENT OF THE NETHERLANDS

PH.D. PROJECT

Research Proposal

Rens Kievit, M.Sc.

supervised by
Prof.Dr. Mirjam VAN REISEN
Prof.Dr. Anna FENSEL
Monique BLOM

May 6, 2024

version 0.1.0

This document contains the research proposal for the PhD project of Rens Kievit. He is a Dual PhD candidate in the Ministry of the Interior and Kingdom Relations of the Government of the Netherlands in cooperation with the Leiden University Medical Center.

Table of Contents

1	Introduction	3
2	Problem Statement	4
2.1	Synthesis	4
2.2	Research Objectives	4
2.3	Research Questions	4
3	Theoretical Framework	6
3.1	Context	6
3.2	Semantic Web	6
3.3	Theory of Change	7
4	Research Design	9
4.1	Research Philosophy	9
4.2	Methodology	9
4.2.1	Case Study	10
4.2.2	Design-Oriented Science	11
4.2.3	Research Process	12
4.3	First Case Study	17
4.3.1	Context	17
5	Ethical Considerations	18
6	Data Management Plan	18
7	Timeline	19

Document History

Version	Date	Author	Comment
0.0.1	19-03-2024	R. Kievit	Copied Lit. Review & Problem Statement documents into here, added first draft of research design. Included first draft of verification section in LR.
0.0.2	17-04-2024	R. Kievit	Removed Lit. Review from document, reorganized structure. Completely revised methodology and theoretical framework, expanded ethical considerations.
0.0.3	23-04-2024	R. Kievit	Incorporated feedback from GAIC peer group. Various notes still left in text.
0.1.0	30-04-2024	R. Kievit	First full draft version. Minor revisions, complete clean-up. Changed versioning to three digit code.

1 Introduction

Public administrations handle enormous volumes of data in order to fulfill their legal obligations. This data is often stored in many different silos that are unable to efficiently communicate with each other. Enabling re-use through data sharing and interoperability can greatly increase the efficiency of a government in performing its tasks. However, which information can be shared with whom should be carefully considered. Most of the data generated by a public administration can be made publicly available, however there are many cases where access should be restricted such as when personal privacy or national security play a role. Ideally, automated authentication and authorization mechanisms should be put in place to ensure safe, privacy-preserving communication of data.

The field of authorization has been the focus of many works since the 1950's. In recent decades, concepts of the Semantic Web have slowly been integrated in various implementations. The Semantic Web is a promising technology capable of enabling, among many other benefits, interoperability between (distributed) heterogeneous data sources largely through the use of rich semantic metadata.

No consensus yet exists regarding the design of a semantics-based, dynamic and distributed architecture for authorization. Some examples of current approaches are: a centralized mechanism which makes authorization decisions based on access policies, user- and data attributes, and potentially context variables (Arshad et al., 2022; Hilia et al., 2017; Kamateri et al., 2014; Khan et al., 2017; Bader et al., 2021); the exploitation of patterns in the linked data graphs stored on Solid Personal Data Stores (Werbrouck et al., 2020); an expansion of the SPARQL query language to protect guarded data by inferring the intent of a data request (Stojanov et al., 2018); and an automatic agent-based model that infers roles, objects and permissions from the data structures (Aslam et al., 2020). These approaches all work in different perspectives and settings.

Another issue in current literature is that there is little emphasis on the role of data subjects (read: humans) in authorizing access to their own information. The work by Villata et al. (2013) allows users to manage who has access to their posts in the context of a Social Semantic Web; Pinto and Prazeres (2024) introduce the Fog of Things (FoT)-Personal Data Stores (PDS) paradigm where sensor data is stored in a Solid PDS under the control of the data subject, however their work is limited in scope.

The works described here are only concepts and experimental implementations with in some cases brief evaluation methods. Arshad et al. (2022) and Stojanov et al. (2018) evaluated their mechanisms based on self-defined principles for a semantic authorization model, Bader et al. (2021) performed an attack-vector analysis to assess the security against malicious actors, and Pinto and Prazeres (2024) briefly discuss how their concept holds up when compared against relevant articles of the GDPR. However, in order to most effectively evaluate a conceptual mechanism, one should implement and investigate it in a real-life situation to uncover unforeseen problems ¹

¹For an example of this, see van Reisen et al. (2021)

2 Problem Statement

2.1 Synthesis

The Dutch government is currently facing problems ranging from low transparency to challenges managing personal identifiable information. This highlights the need for major improvements or changes in existing data management systems. An important prerequisite for proper data management is the implementation of proper access control models. Distributed technologies provide a potential solution path, however research into the implementation of these technologies for authorization is mostly limited to theory. In this work we will investigate these existing technologies and attempt to design mechanisms that are applicable to real world scenarios.

2.2 Research Objectives

Main Research Objective: Implement and evaluate distributed, semantic and dynamic authorization mechanisms within a public administration.

- RO1.** Create a mapping of the properties of existing distributed, semantic and dynamic authorization mechanisms.
- RO2.** Define in which contexts these mechanisms are applicable, and delineate potential gaps.
- RO3.** Assess the role of data subjects in exerting control over their sensitive information within different specific settings.
- RO4.** Design and implement authorization mechanisms in at least four real-world settings in different data-use contexts within a public administration.
- RO5.** Evaluate the process of the design and implementation phases, and the performance of the implemented model.

2.3 Research Questions

Main Research Question: How can a semantic and dynamic authorization mechanism be implemented to automatically ensure compliance with data protection regulations in a public administration?.

- RQ1.** What are the state of the art distributed, semantic and dynamic authorization mechanisms in research and industry?
- RQ2.** When are these existing authorization mechanisms applicable, and when should new methodology be developed?
- RQ3.** What role, if any, can data subjects play in controlling protected data pertaining to them?

- RQ4.** What are challenges in implementing distributed and semantic authorization mechanisms in various real-world settings within a public administration?
- RQ5.** How can these challenges and lessons inform a broader implementation?

3 Theoretical Framework

In this section we describe some of the concepts used in this research. We start by describing the way in which we look at the problem of the data management system of the Government of the Netherlands in [subsection 3.1](#), then describe the background behind the path we have chosen for our solution space in [subsection 3.2](#). Finally in [subsection 3.3](#) we describe the theoretical model we will use in this work to think about enacting change and innovation through this research.

3.1 Context

The current state of the data management system of the Government of the Netherlands² and the issues in the public domain that are caused by its shortcomings can be described as a "wicked problem". This term, coined by [Rittel and Webber \(1973\)](#) describes a problem that is immensely big in size, complexity and impact. A wicked problem is characterized by the fact that it cannot be encapsulated, and therefore there is no "true" solution to it. Many perspectives on a wicked problem can be justified and each of these different perspectives can lead to different solutions, which can be of varying "goodness" ([Buchanan, 1992](#); [Skaburskis, 2008](#)). Our task therefore lies in understanding the problem and its stakeholders and the possible solution paths as precisely as possible in order to propose a way forward. Our method of understanding the problem and its stakeholders is further described in [subsection 4.2](#), the lens we use to look at the problem space is described in the next section.

3.2 Semantic Web

Because of the reliance of a solution to a wicked problem on the manner in which it is viewed, it is of utmost importance that the lens through which we look at the problem space is explicitly described, and any underlying assumptions understood. In this research we will work with the vision that Tim Berners-Lee, the inventor of the World Wide Web, proposed not long after its inception. This vision is that of the Semantic Web (SW), first discussed by [Berners-Lee \(2000\)](#); [Berners-Lee et al. \(2001\)](#), it is an extension of the current form of the web built on semantic information that enables meaningful computer comprehension and interaction. This is made possible by linking information to persistent locations on the web through Uniform Resource Identifiers (discussed more in-depth in [Berners-Lee \(2010\)](#)) and describing this information using structured knowledge represented by ontologies. [Berners-Lee et al. \(2001\)](#) defines this in the context of the SW as "a document or file that formally defines the relations among terms" (p.9), where this document in itself also lives on the Web as a resource.

²In the Dutch Government we refer to the field of data management as "informatiehuishouding" which translates to "information management". However following the definitions by [Plug et al. \(2022\)](#) these systems mostly deal with data, not information. This is a semantic discrepancy that might warrant further investigation in the future.

They describe the most typical form of ontology as a taxonomy, a hierarchical classification scheme.

More recent developments have seen the SW be endorsed by the World Wide Web Consortium (W3C) who keep track of a set of standards for the technology stack to support the SW (W3C, 2019). Furthermore, various approaches to incorporating these technologies in the current internet are being undertaken such as the decentralized personal data pod based Solid specification founded by Tim Berners-Lee³, or the FAIR principles which describe proper data management techniques, and are based on linked data technologies (Wilkinson et al., 2016; Strawn, 2021). Within the Dutch Government, the Sustainable Accessibility Framework (DUTO-Raamwerk, NA, 2023) also provides a generic design system for data management in part based on semantic technologies. In the course of this research it will be investigated how DUTO and FAIR can be combined into a single framework in cooperation with the National Archive.

If we look at access control through the lens of semantic technologies, a problem immediately arises. While various techniques to manage access have been presented in the literature, as discussed above, no consensus has yet been reached. This is also evident from the set of semantic web standards endorsed by W3C (W3C, 2019) where authorization is notably lacking as of the time of this writing. These points combined motivate an investigation into the design and implementation of semantics-based authorization techniques.

3.3 Theory of Change

In its core, this research is concerned with research and potentially enacting change to tackle challenges over various domains. Because of the strong connection with the Government of the Netherlands, there is also a political aspect to this change. To enable a methodical study of the process, it is important to have a clear vision on how change occurs.

We will base ourselves on the combination of two distinct theories: the Kingdon multiple streams framework (Kingdon, 2010)⁴ and the Overton Window (Mackinac Center, nd). The former describes that for something to appear on the public agenda through a certain time-bound policy window (i.e. be a focus of political discussion that might lead to a policy), three separate streams need to converge. These are: the problem stream, containing issues currently being faced; the political stream, describing the current focus of political discourse; and the policy stream containing possible solutions to a particular problem. In other words, Kingdon (2010) posits that a problem appears on the public agenda if and only if it has garnered political attention, and a possible solution(path) exists. Kingdon (2010) originally described those manipulating the streams, either through devising solutions or through creating political attention, policy entrepreneurs. However in this work we will refer to these actors as *social transformers*.

³<https://solidproject.org/>

⁴The original idea was published by Kingdon in 1984, however it had a major revision leading to the second edition cited here.

Figure 1: Theoretical framework for a theory of change based on the Multiple Streams Framework (Kingdon, 2010) which is extended with the Overton Window (Mackinac Center, nd) where social transformers bring new, innovative ideas into the public view. This stretches the range of acceptable ideas into one direction (indicated by the acceptable and radical ideas turning becoming popular or sensible) which in turn influences the possible solution space in the policy stream.

The Overton Window provides a method of visualizing the streams of Kingdon by differentiating between politically acceptable thoughts (inside the window) and unacceptable thoughts (outside the window). Here we will refer to the window of Overton as the *range of acceptable policies* to avoid confusion with Kingdon’s Policy Window. Trevino (2006) made the levels of acceptability explicit by describing them as a rough continuum from unthinkable to policy. Using the theory of Overton we can think of bringing attention to an issue as shifting or expanding this range. This is mostly applicable to the policy stream as we have less control over the political discourse or problems that occur (Hofer, 2022). Focusing down further, we will use this concept in this research to think about the acceptance of Semantic Web and Linked Data technologies in the context of the Dutch Government.

In this context, a social transformer can either directly impact the policy stream by working on solutions that fall within the current range of acceptable policies, or innovate in regions that currently fall outside this range and actively work towards shifting or expanding it to encapsulate the new solutions, which thereby influences the policy stream by changing what is acceptable for the

public. A graphical overview of this combined theory of change is provided in [Figure 1](#).

4 Research Design

4.1 Research Philosophy

In this research we will utilize a constructivistic philosophy to the collection of knowledge. The research will be carried out through various case studies, in which the context is of great importance to ensure a good connection between the field and the theoretical solutions we bring to the table as academics. This will mostly be done through codesign sessions with relevant stakeholders from the community.

In this approach it is important to consider the role of the researcher as an instrumental part of the outcome of the research. This supports the constructivistic way of looking at the manner of knowledge collection in this research.

This is of greatest importance when considering the cross-case study analysis, and the possibilities for transferable knowledge in this work. While not completely absent, this transferable knowledge is not necessarily guaranteed and will require careful introspection. As will be presented in the next section, we have introduced a specific phase in the research procedure to allow room for this introspection from a more general point of view.

4.2 Methodology

Because of the wicked nature of the problem we are dealing with it is impossible to discover some absolute truth that easily solves the situation. If we look at the ten characteristics set out by [Rittel and Webber \(1973\)](#) we can draw a few conclusions that are of relevance to this research along three distinct axes:

1. **Problem Axis:** Every wicked problem is unique and cannot be exhaustively bound or formulated.
2. **Solution Axis:** The manner in which one explains a wicked problem influences the resolution. This uniqueness leads to the fact that a solution cannot be absolutely verified.
3. **Implementation Axis:** Implementing a solution to a wicked problem is a 'one-shot' operation.

While unsolvable by their very nature, we should aim to minimize the uncertainty along each of these axes through our methodology. We will do this by utilizing multiple case studies to restrict the scope of the problem with which we are dealing, thereby minimizing along the problem axis. Within each of these case studies we will use collaborative design-oriented science approaches to iteratively approach solutions to the problems. The cooperation with the

community is an essential factor here as it allows for a broader view of a problem, from multiple reference points, thereby leading to a more representative solution. In the following sections we will further expand on both of these methods and how they will be implemented in this research.

4.2.1 Case Study

Case studies have been utilized in many research projects, spread out over various domains. The goal of a case study is to perform a detailed study of a particular situation. This provides more specificity at the cost of generalizability. The goal of using case studies in this research is to sample the wicked problem space through manageable issues where a solution can feasibly be designed, implemented and evaluated. Through multiple case studies we hope to decrease along the problem axis within any single study, and simultaneously increase our final findings along the problem axis through representability over multiple studies.

These case studies will take place within various organisations spread out over multiple departments within the Dutch Government. They will be collected through the *multidisciplinary teams for information management* (MDT-IHH), which is a group within the Dutch Government with knowledge about data management and is hired by other organisations to assist in various related tasks and problems. Within the six year time frame of this proposed research, we want to perform at least four different case studies. This should align with the typical duration of a task of the MDT-IHH, six to twelve months.

The case studies will ideally increase in complexity over the duration of the PhD such that we can slowly build upon previous findings. Currently we envision the following progression:

1. An indexing system, similar to a library or archive.
2. Non-personal data used for operations or research.
3. A system containing personal information that needs to be used by both civil servants and civilians.
4. A fully dynamic system containing all of the above.

To increase the generalizability of the resolutions of these case studies with respect to the entire Government of the Netherlands, we want to employ them in a range of contexts to get a sense of the requirements of different types of organisations with respect to data management, and specifically access control, through a cross-case study analysis. This means that we want to perform our case studies at least at an executive organisation (e.g. social security), a policy organisation and a supporting organisation (e.g. internal finances).

As described in [subsection 4.3](#), there is a case study already planned at The National Library of the Netherlands which falls into the first complexity category, but does not fall into any of the context categories given above. However it is still very useful because they have an advanced data management system

based on semantic technologies which allows for simpler design and deployment of authorization techniques, and a very clear problem that can be solved using an explicit permission structure.

Details of later case studies are unknown as of the time of this writing and will be very dependent on which organisations both experience problems related to data management that can be solved with authorization techniques, and their capacity to support this research. During the selection procedures throughout this research, we will aim to tackle at least four case studies that cover each of the complexity and context points given above.

4.2.2 Design-Oriented Science

This research lies at an intersection between the creation of new academic knowledge and the improvement of real-world practices through the design of new solutions. Because of this the field of design-oriented research is a very natural fit as it aims to provide methodologies to connect these two fields that are unconnected in traditional research methodologies. This field is defined by (van Turnhout et al., 2023) to be

- Driven by real-world issues.
- Focused on designing solutions.
- Striving for (re)usability across contexts.
- Measuring success on desirability and operability of the solution.

In their (Dutch-only) book "Handbook design-oriented scientific research" van Turnhout et al. (2023) provide various models for structuring a design-oriented research. The fundamental model is the Three Process Model (TPM) which divides the research into three separate streams (Cremers and van Turnhout, 2023). This model is presented in Figure 2. At the extremes are the knowledge process, which is akin to traditional science with its focus on developing new theories, and the practice process, which is focused on solving issues or improving practices. In between these two extremes is the binding process with its focus on innovation.

In this research this process will be envisioned as researchers, practitioners and potentially designers collaboratively going through an (iterative) design process which is both grounded in theory and applicable to the problems arising in practice to create a core design. This core design can be represented by an exhaustive set of design principles and guidelines which capture the solution envisioned in the design process. This can then be further abstracted to lead to transferable knowledge regarding the core design and the process that lead to it, and further specified, created and implemented to improve the practice.

For the design of the research we will also utilize the DOT-Framework (van Turnhout et al., 2014; van Turnhout and Lusse, 2023) which sets out five research strategies along two different axes. This framework is presented in Figure 3. Along the vertical axis there is a differentiation between completeness

Figure 2: The Three Processes Model, translated from Dutch based on Fig. 1 in [Cremers and van Turnhout \(2023\)](#).

(exploration) and certainty (validation), the horizontal axis runs from relevance (field) to rigor (theory). Along the horizontal axis the authors differentiate between three regimes: the practical context; the innovation space; and the knowledgebase. These three regimes exactly correspond to the three streams presented in the Three Process Model. As is clearly visible in [Figure 3](#) the research strategy of Integrative Design, situated in the center of the framework, is where all the different strategies are combined either by providing a solid foundation through the exploration strategies, or through correspondence with field and theory through validation. The five different circles provided in the framework are only research strategies, it is up to the researcher themselves to connect fitting methodology to each of these phases.

For both the DOT-Framework and the Three Process Model it is not absolutely required to separate each of the streams or strategies (although in some scenarios this could be desirable). Rather they provide a framework to think about the research procedure and the choice of approaches and methodologies, and let us ensure that throughout the entire research, and within smaller sub-steps within this, we cover each of the processes as in TPM or all of the extremes of the DOT-Framework. In doing so we ensure that the research most effectively contributes to both academic research and to real world practices.

4.2.3 Research Process

In [Figure 4](#) we present the structure of this research as a flow through the DOT-Framework ([van Turnhout et al., 2014](#)). Separate steps are indicated by digits and their connections are indicated by arrows, not all steps are necessarily sequential as indicated by some arrows pointing in both directions. In [Table 1](#) the goal of each step is indicated along with the associated methodology and its

Figure 3: The DOT-Framework, translated from Dutch based on Fig. 1 in [van Turnhout et al. \(2014\)](#)

connection to the research questions outlined at the beginning of this document.

We identify four distinct phases in this research. The first is the theoretical preparation, consisting of steps 1 and 2 and indicated by solid arrows. In this phase we aim to build a solid theoretical foundation by identifying (step 1) and classifying (step 2) authorization mechanisms and thereby building up the *solution repertoire* ([Van Turnhout and Smits, 2021](#)).

The next phase, which will most likely occur simultaneously with the first, is the design phase consisting of steps 3 and 4 with their connection indicated by long-dashed arrows. Here we start by understanding the business context using field exploration techniques (step 3) and follow this up with the creation of a core design in co-creation/design sessions (step 4). It is possible to move back from the design step into the exploratory step if further knowledge of the business context is required. At the end of this phase we should have a core design that is ready to be implemented in the case-study context in the form of a Minimal Viable Product (MVP).

This is then followed by the evaluation phase, consisting of steps 5 and 6 and indicated by short-dashed arrows. Here we implement the core design created in the design phase and evaluate this in the field through various types of user tests (step 5). Here it is possible to return to the design phase if any major problems arise. After the field tests we verify the implementation from an academic perspective, such as through a peer-reviewed article (step 6). If any problems arise in this step, it is possible (resources allowing) to return to the design phase and create a new core design.

The final phase in each case-study is the sustain phase, covered by step 7 and indicated by the dotted arrows. Here we aim to enhance the sustainability of both the work done in the case study through off-boarding techniques, and enhance the quality of the research through introspection. For the latter point we will review the process of the case studies, perform cross-case analyses and attempt to draw transferable knowledge from this. This is also the phase where we can start preparing for the next case study by investigating what knowledge we would still like to gather and by adjusting things in the methodology based on the lessons learned.

Figure 4: The steps and phases of this research plotted on the DOT-Framework (van Turnhout et al., 2014). Further explanation of the structure of the phases is given in subsection 4.2.3, with descriptions of goals, applied methodology and connection to the research questions given in Table 1.

Step	Phase	Goal	Methodology	RQ
1	Theoretical Preparation	A.M. model discovery	Systematic literature review Expert interviews	1
2	Theoretical Preparation	A.M. mapping	Literature search Present to expert panels	2, 3
3	Design	Understand business context	Participating observations Explorative (group) interviews	2
4	Design	Create a core design	(Iterative) co-creation/-design sessions	3, 4
5	Evaluation	Implementation evaluation	User tests (surveys, interviews, usage data)	3, 4
6	Evaluation	Within-case analysis	Literature review (theoretical validation) Expert interviews	3, 4
7	Sustain	Cross-case analysis	x	5

Table 1: The steps and phases shown visually in [Figure 4](#) combined with brief description of their goals, associated data collection methodologies and the connection to the research questions.

4.3 First Case Study

At the time of writing the location for the first case study is already known. Here we describe the context of the case study and plan out the first steps to sketch a generic image for the iterative phase of this research. This section is only limited to the first case study as the later studies are as of yet unknown.

4.3.1 Context

The first study will be performed at The National Library of the Netherlands (KB).⁵ They currently have a Linked Open Data (LOD) store containing, among others, the descriptions of all publications that were made in or about the Netherlands or were written in Dutch, and information regarding the relevant authors (KB, nd). Through a SPARQL endpoint these data are completely queryable. Various other datasets such as the KB alba amicorum ('album of friends') or a collection of catchpenny prints are also stored as LOD queryable with SPARQL.

Of relevance to this project are the first two datasets, the complete Dutch bibliography referred to as NDT and the Dutch thesaurus of author names referred to as NTA. The NDT currently only describes bibliographic information of its publications, this can be the year of publication, the author and potentially a brief description of the book. This is the metadata of the book. The data itself, i.e. the contents of the book, are not included in this store because they can not always be made publicly available. This is because the text of a book can fall under Dutch author's rights (Min. JenV, 2022).⁶ This states that the right to publication or distribution of a work belongs solely to the maker of that work, or their lawful successors.

There are two main methods to allow a book to be visible (either publicly, or to a specific subset of people). The first is described in the author's rights article 37 which states that the copyright of an author on a work expires 70 years after their death counted from the first of January in the year after their death. After this time period, all their works are made publicly available. The second is through licenses and/or contracts. This can either be a Creative Commons licence which enables broad re-use of information, or through contracts which could for example stipulate the use of a specific subset of protected literature by a specific research institute for a specific amount of time.

These possibilities are however not yet incorporated in the LOD store of the KB. Their current approach to ensure compliance is by excluding all literature from the public store. On the other end of the spectrum, a person that wants to access protected literature can sign a personal contract with the KB which allows them full access to all data. Our hypothesis is that by implementing automated permission rules in the LOD store we can allow for more granular access control while ensuring adherence to all relevant regulations and agreements.

⁵From 'Koninklijke Bibliotheek' which translates directly to Royal Library

⁶The original law was accepted in 1912, here we cite the latest amendment as of the time of this writing as this is what is currently relevant.

This project has not yet started at the time of this writing, but will most likely begin somewhere in 2024.

5 Ethical Considerations

We strive for open source science through transparency in both research procedure and in data. However, as is the main focus of this research proposal, not all data can be made publicly available. During this project it is possible that confidential data will be used for testing purposes. Nevertheless, for the sake of openness we will use simple mock data or synthetic data for published implementations as much as possible, and note any areas where private data possibly influenced design choices.

If synthetic data will be used in this project it is important to acknowledge the trade-off between representation of the underlying information, and data protection. It will be important to carefully consider which attributes are required and to make sure that this complies to data protection regulations, potentially through an external committee.

Another large area of ethical care needs to be taken in the field of participatory research, embodied here through interviews, observation and codesign. First, the field participants of the research need to be informed of the research so that they can provide their informed consent. Care also needs to be taken to ensure participants in interviews or codesign sessions feel comfortable in their role. They should feel free to share their thoughts and ideas without fear of backlash (from other participants, researchers or the community). These two points require proper contracts to be setup before hand to set the boundaries for the conversation, and a good data management plan on the side of the researcher to ensure proper data handling.

Finally, the role of the researcher in a design-oriented research also needs to be made clear for themselves. As extensively discussed by [Akkerman et al. \(2013\)](#) it can be difficult to both be a participant in a team while simultaneously fulfilling the role of researcher. Clear boundaries will need to be set to both avoid confusion and allow for scientific integrity.

6 Data Management Plan

Before starting any data collection methods that collect information that can be related to a specific person (e.g. interviews, extensive surveys or user tests) we will create contracts containing a data use agreement. In this contract it will be important to explicitly describe the goals for which the data will be collected, and how long it will be stored. The former will be provided based on the research question or -phase for which the data is collected, while the latter will typically be the PhD project as we will most likely require access to information on which results are based until the acceptance of the final dissertation at the end of the PhD.

To further enhance privacy we will store information such as transcribed interviews or individual survey results in an anonymized fashion on a local store with access restricted to the relevant researchers. Following GDPR, participants should also be able to see their own information, and request for certain information to be removed if they believe it to be compromising.

To promote open science, this project will utilize showyourwork! (Luger et al., 2021)⁷ as much as possible according to privacy regulations, an open-source workflow management tool designed to make open-source research articles reproducible, extensible and transparent. The showyourwork! workflow works on a GitHub page dedicated to a specific article that contains a conda environment file, scripts for data processing and creation and figure creation, rules to collect data from Zenodo or create it (using the previously mentioned scripts) and the manuscript as L^AT_EX files. The resulting article is dynamically created as a PDF using snakemake (Mölder et al., 2021).

7 Timeline

The entire PhD has a runtime of six years in the period 2024-2030, within this time frame approximately one third of my time can be spent on the research project (i.e. 12 hours per week). An initial planning overview is presented in Table 2. The 'steps' column in this table corresponds to the research design steps shown in Figure 4 and Table 1. As is visible in the figure, steps 3-7 are cyclical in their design as they have to be covered anew in each case study. Step 7 (cross-case analysis) appears both in each case study, and also separately at the end of the PhD. While in both cases this is both part of the same step, the goals are slightly different in each context. As a concluding part of a single case study, step 7 is used to reflect on the study and inform future studies. While as a concluding part of the PhD it will be used to draw generalizable conclusions regarding the design process.

As is visible in the table, the proposed publishing structure of this research is different than is typical for a PhD where one research question corresponds to one paper. Because of the multiple case study approach in this work, with multiple research questions being covered in each case study, the publishing waters can get mucky. The proposal here is to publish at least a peer-reviewed article about the preparatory work (RQ1/2), and then one article about each of the case studies (RQ3/4), a final article can then be written which answers RQ5. In the first two types of articles it is important to explicitly describe which sections of the paper answers which research question.

⁷Cited at the recommendation of the creators of showyourwork!. While not an article dedicated to describing the tool, it is its first use-case. More information can be found at <https://show-your.work/en/latest/>.

Activity / Milestone	Step	Deadline
Completion of research proposal.		April 2024
Find and map authorization mechanisms onto theoretical framework (RQ1). ¹	1	July 2024
Define applicable contexts and gaps of authorization mechanisms (RQ2). ¹	2	October 2024
Paper 1 submittable (RQ1,2).	1,2	December 2024
Start of project 1. ²	3-5	Q1 2025
Paper 2 about project 1 submittable.	6,7	Q4 2025
Start of project 2.	3-5	Q1 2026
Paper 3 about project 2 submittable.	6,7	Q4 2026
Start of project 3.	3-5	Q1 2027
Paper 4 about project 3 submittable.	6,7	Q4 2027
Start of project 4.	3-5	Q1 2028
Paper 5 about project 4 submittable.	6,7	Q4 2028
Cross-case analysis	7	Q2 2029
Completion of dissertation.		Q4 2029
Preparation for PhD Defence.		Q1 - Q2 2030

Table 2: First rough time planning for major milestones in this PhD project.

¹: This will most likely involve meetings and interviews with various stakeholders and experts. ²: As of this writing there are talks about starting project 1 in Q2/3 of 2024. This is entirely possible but requires correct focus in various stages of the project and this PhD.

References

- Koninklijke Bibliotheek (KB) (n.d.). Lod view. <https://data.bibliotheken.nl/>. Accessed: 2024-03-26.
- Ministerie van Justitie en Veiligheid (Min. JenV) (2022). Auteurswet. *Staatsblad*, 345. Accessed: 2024-03-26.
- World Wide Web Consortium (W3C) (2019). Semantic web standards. https://www.w3.org/2001/sw/wiki/Main_Page. Accessed 2024-03-27.
- Akkerman, S. F., Bronkhorst, L. H., and Zitter, I. (2013). The complexity of educational design research. *Quality & Quantity*, 47(1):421–439.
- Arshad, H., Johansen, C., and Owe, O. (2022). Semantic attribute-based access control: A review on current status and future perspectives. *Journal of Systems Architecture*, 129:102625.
- Aslam, S., Ahmed, M., Ahmed, I., Khan, A., Ahmad, A., Imran, M., Anjum, A., and Hussain, S. (2020). Obac: towards agent-based identification and classification of roles, objects, permissions (rop) in distributed environment. *Multimedia Tools Appl.*, 79(45–46):34363–34384.
- Bader, L., Pennekamp, J., Matzutt, R., Hedderich, D., Kowalski, M., Lücken, V., and Wehrle, K. (2021). Blockchain-based privacy preservation for supply chains supporting lightweight multi-hop information accountability. *Information Processing & Management*, 58(3):102529.
- Berners-Lee, T. (2000). *Weaving the Web: The Original Design and Ultimate Destiny of the World Wide Web*.
- Berners-Lee, T. (2010). Linked data (revised version). <https://www.w3.org/DesignIssues/LinkedData.html>. Accessed 2024-03-27.
- Berners-Lee, T., Hendler, J., and Lasilla, O. (2001). The semantic web. *Scientific American Magazine*, 284.
- Buchanan, R. (1992). Wicked problems in design thinking. *Design Issues*, 8:5–21.
- Cremers, P. and van Turnhout, K. (2023). Structureren van ontwerpgericht onderzoek (hoofdstuk 7). In Turnhout, K., Andriessen, D., and Cremers, P., editors, *Handboek ontwerpgericht wetenschappelijk onderzoek. Ontwerpend onderzoeken in sociale contexten (2e druk)*., pages 99–116. Boom.
- Hilia, M., Chibani, A., Winter, T., and Djouani, K. (2017). Semantic based authorization framework for multi-domain collaborative cloud environments. *Procedia Computer Science*, 109:718–724. 8th International Conference on Ambient Systems, Networks and Technologies, ANT-2017 and the 7th International Conference on Sustainable Energy Information Technology, SEIT 2017, 16-19 May 2017, Madeira, Portugal.

- Hoefler, R. (2022). The multiple streams framework: Understanding and applying the problems, policies, and politics approach. *Journal of Policy Practice and Research*, 3:1–5.
- Kamateri, E., Kalampokis, E., Tambouris, E., and Tarabanis, K. (2014). The linked medical data access control framework. *J Biomed Inform*, 50:213–225.
- Khan, Y., Saleem, M., Mehdi, M., Hogan, A., Mehmood, Q., Rebholz-Schuhmann, D., and Sahay, R. (2017). SAFE: SPARQL federation over RDF data cubes with access control. *Journal of Biomedical Semantics*, 8(1):5.
- Kingdon, J. W. (2010). *Agendas, Alternatives, And Public Policies (2nd edition)*. Pearson.
- Luger, R., Bedell, M., Foreman-Mackey, D., Crossfield, I. J. M., Zhao, L. L., and Hogg, D. W. (2021). Mapping stellar surfaces III: An Efficient, Scalable, and Open-Source Doppler Imaging Model. *arXiv e-prints*, page arXiv:2110.06271.
- Mackinac Center (n.d.). A brief explanation of the overtone window. <https://www.mackinac.org/OvertoneWindow>. Accessed on 2024-04-16.
- Mölder, F., Jablonski, K., Letcher, B., Hall, M., Tomkins-Tinch, C., Sochat, V., Forster, J., Lee, S., Twardziok, S., Kanitz, A., Wilm, A., Holtgrewe, M., Rahmann, S., Nahnsen, S., and Köster, J. (2021). Sustainable data analysis with snakemake [version 2; peer review: 2 approved]. *F1000Research*, 10(33).
- Nationaal Archief (NA) (2023). Duto-raamwerk. <https://www.nationaalarchief.nl/archiveren/kennisbank/duto-raamwerk>. Accessed: 2024-04-23.
- Pinto, G. P. and Prazeres, C. (2024). Towards data privacy in a fog of things. *Internet Technology Letters*, n/a(n/a):e512. e512 ITL-23-0238.R3.
- Plug, R., Liang, Y., Aktau, A., Basajja, M., Oladipo, F., and van Reisen, M. (2022). Terminology for a FAIR Framework for the Virus Outbreak Data Network-Africa. *Data Intelligence*, 4(4):698–723.
- Rittel, H. W. J. and Webber, M. M. (1973). Dilemmas in a general theory of planning. *Policy Sciences*, 4(2):155–169.
- Skaburskis, A. (2008). The origin of “wicked problems”. *Planning Theory & Practice*, 9:277–280. Discusses the origin of the term ‘wicked problem’ and puts it in context.
- Stojanov, R., Gramatikov, S., Mishkovski, I., and Trajanov, D. (2018). Linked data authorization platform. *IEEE Access*, 6:1189–1213.
- Strawn, G. (2021). 75 years of astonishing evolution of it: 1946–2021. *IT Professional*, 23:21–27.

- Trevino, J. (2006). The overton window. <https://web.archive.org/web/20060716000532/http://www.swordscrossed.org/?p=50>. Archived version of 2006-07-16. Accessed on 2024-04-09.
- van Reisen, M., Oladipo, F., Stokmans, M., Mpezamihgo, M., Folorunso, S., Schultes, E., Basajja, M., Aktau, A., Amare, S. Y., Taye, G. T., Purnama Jati, P. H., Chindoza, K., Wirtz, M., Ghardallou, M., van Stam, G., Ayele, W., Nalugala, R., Abdullahi, I., Osigwe, O., Graybeal, J., Medhanyie, A. A., Kawu, A. A., Liu, F., Wolstencroft, K., Flikkenschild, E., Lin, Y., Stocker, J., and Musen, M. A. (2021). Design of a fair digital data health infrastructure in africa for covid-19 reporting and research. *Advanced Genetics*, 2(2):e10050.
- van Turnhout, K., Andriessen, D., and Cremers, P. (2023). *Handboek ontwerpergericht wetenschappelijk onderzoek. Ontwerpend onderzoeken in sociale contexten (2e druk)*. Boom.
- van Turnhout, K., Bennis, A., Craenmehr, S., Holwerda, R., Jacobs, M., Niels, R., Zaad, L., Hoppenbrouwers, S., Lenior, D., and Bakker, R. (2014). Design patterns for mixed-method research in hci. In *Proceedings of the 8th Nordic Conference on Human-Computer Interaction: Fun, Fast, Foundational*, NordiCHI '14, page 361–370, New York, NY, USA. Association for Computing Machinery.
- van Turnhout, K. and Lusse, M. (2023). Ontwerpen van de onderzoeksaanpak (hoofdstuk 11). In Turnhout, K., Andriessen, D., and Cremers, P., editors, *Handboek ontwerpergericht wetenschappelijk onderzoek. Ontwerpend onderzoeken in sociale contexten (2e druk)*., pages 155–170. Boom.
- Van Turnhout, K. and Smits, A. (2021). Solution repertoire.
- Villata, S., Costabello, L., Delaforge, N., and Gandon, F. (2013). A social semantic web access control model. *Journal on Data Semantics*, 2(1):21–36.
- Werbrouck, J., Taelman, R., Verborgh, R., Pauwels, P., Beetz, J., and Mannens, E. (2020). Pattern-based access control in a decentralised collaboration environment. In *Proceedings of the 8th Linked Data in Architecture and Construction Workshop*, CEUR Workshop Proceedings.
- Wilkinson, M. D., Dumontier, M., Aalbersberg, I. J., Appleton, G., Axton, M., Baak, A., Blomberg, N., Boiten, J.-W., da Silva Santos, L. B., Bourne, P. E., and et al. (2016). The fair guiding principles for scientific data management and stewardship. *Scientific Data*, 3(1).